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Mapping chemical footprints of organic micropollutants in European streams

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ABSTRACT

There is increasing awareness that chemical pollution of freshwater systems with complex mixtures of chemicals from domestic sources, agriculture and industry may cause a substantial chemical footprint on water organisms, pushing aquatic ecosystems outside the safe operating space. The present study defines chemical footprints as the risk that chemicals or chemical mixtures will have adverse effects on a specific group of organisms. The aim is to characterise these chemical footprints in European streams based on a unique and uniform screening of more than 600 chemicals in 445 surface water samples, and to derive site- and compound-specific information for management prioritisation purposes. In total, 504 pesticides, biocides, pharmaceuticals and other compounds have been detected, including frequently occurring and site-specific compounds with concentrations up to 74 µg/L. Key finding is that three-quarter of the investigated sites in 22 European river basins exceed established thresholds for chemical footprints in freshwater, leading to expected acute or chronic impacts on aquatic organisms. The largest footprints were recorded on invertebrates, followed by algae and fish. More than 70 chemicals exceed thresholds of chronic impacts on invertebrates. For all organism groups, pesticides and biocides were the main drivers of chemical footprints, while mixture impacts were particularly relevant for invertebrates. No clear significant correlation was found between chemical footprints and the urban discharge fractions, suggesting that effluent-specific quality rather than the total load of treated wastewater in the aquatic environment and the contribution of diffuse sources, e.g. from agriculture, determine chemical footprints.

1. Introduction

Awareness is rising that human activities progressively impact on earth's complex systems, pushing them outside planetary and regional boundaries and thus the safe operating space for humanity. These boundaries are quantified and clearly exceeded for climate change, biodiversity loss and the global nitrogen cycle (Rockström et al., 2009). At the same time, there is increasing evidence that humanity operates outside the safe space also for chemical pollution (Cousins et al., 2022; Persson et al., 2022; Richardson et al., 2023) and that there is an urgent need for action based on continental and global scale knowledge on exposure and impacts of chemicals (Brack et al., 2022). Local and

planetary boundaries for chemical pollution may be defined as the space where chemical pressure remains within regional or global carrying capacities, respectively, thus not disrupting essential ecosystem functions (Kosnik et al., 2022). Similar to carbon and water footprints, chemical footprint approaches have been proposed to quantify the pressure of chemical emissions on ecosystems versus carrying capacities by translating chemical concentrations to risk indicators such as multi-substance potential affected fractions of species (msPAF) (Zijp et al., 2014) or cumulative toxic units (\sum TU) (Finckh et al., 2022a; Sprague, 1970; von der Ohe et al., 2009). Using the msPAF approach, chronic and acute toxic pressure of modelled mixture exposures have been mapped for more than 22,000 European water bodies (Posthuma et al., 2019).

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Within the last decade, an increasing number of studies on screening micropollutants such as pharmaceuticals (Wilkinson et al., 2022), pesticides (Liess et al., 2021; Mahler et al., 2021; Munz et al., 2017) and multiple chemicals (Carmona and Picó, 2018; Kandje et al., 2020; Peng et al., 2018) on a regional to global scale have been performed. Recently, 83 monitoring studies from several continents were reviewed in order to prioritise micropollutants in water environments which deserve more attention globally (Yang et al., 2022). Based on these data, the authors identified 182 micropollutants posing toxic risks at the concentrations measured in the evaluated case studies.

The origin of these micropollutants is diverse, ranging from private households and industry typically connected to the public sewage system to urban and agricultural run-off. Many organic micropollutants, such as pesticides, pharmaceuticals and personal care products, hormones or industrial chemicals can pass the common wastewater treatment process because of incomplete removal or bypass treatment via stormwater overflows and are thus discharged into our freshwater systems (Carmona et al., 2014; Finckh et al., 2022a; Kienle et al., 2019; Kostich et al., 2014; Loos et al., 2013; Neale et al., 2017). Urban and agricultural run-off, emissions from livestock farming and from industrial spills may lead to direct surface or groundwater contamination (Meyer et al., 2019). Varying fractions of treated or untreated wastewater, treatment performance, consumer behaviour (sales quantity) as well as chemicals fate may impact on the environmental occurrence of emerging pollutants. Detection frequencies and chemical concentrations have also been found to depend on the stream order, season and rain events (Halbach et al., 2021). However, while knowledge on contamination of water environments and its sources is increasing, studies mapping chronic and acute toxic pressure based on consistently measured concentrations of a larger set of chemicals on a European scale are widely lacking. Likewise, this holds true for interdisciplinary approaches combining the occurrence of chemicals with additional hydrological parameters, such as stream order, flow regimes or urban discharge fraction (Büttner et al., 2022; Büttner et al., 2020).

For Europe, Malaj et al. (2014) integrated for the first time monitoring data on the continental scale for evaluating toxic pressure on aquatic ecosystems and found that almost half of the European water bodies faced chronic toxic risks. The underlying governmental monitoring data were rather comprehensive in spatial coverage and included more than 4,000 European sites, however were very inhomogeneous in terms of the chemicals analysed per site, ranging from 3 to 241 compounds. This inconsistent and often small number of chemicals probably resulted in an underestimation of toxic pressure indicated by a clear correlation between the numbers of potentially hazardous chemicals analysed and estimated risks.

Thus, for the present study, we exploited a unique dataset of consistently measured environmental concentrations of 610 analysed chemicals from a set of 445 surface water samples combined from different sampling campaigns in 22 European countries. The measured organic micropollutants were characterised according to their frequency of detection, concentrations and their related toxic pressure, here defined as the chemical footprint. The target compounds were selected based on their previous detection in surface waters and their accessibility to liquid chromatography high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS) screening approaches. They include most relevant water contaminants such as pesticides, biocides, pharmaceuticals and many industrial compounds, while metals and very hydrophobic chemicals such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and typical legacy persistent organic pollutants could not be considered. Risks from mixtures of chemicals were mapped as \sum TU (Sprague, 1970; Von der Ohe et al., 2009), providing organism group-specific estimates of chemical footprints for algae, crustaceans and fish in different river basins and in water bodies of different stream orders. Wastewater discharge was hypothesised to be one of the major pollution sources of European surface waters. Thus, surface water concentrations of the detected chemicals were related to typical wastewater treatment plant (WWTP)

effluent concentrations as well as to urban discharge fractions (UDF) in the rivers.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Sample information

In this study, surface water from 22 European countries and 22 different river basins was collected and combined into a unique set of 445 water samples (SI Appendix B, Table B.1) (Finckh and Carmona et al., 2023). It comprises a large variety of different samples in terms of stream order, season, geographical location and anthropogenic influence (i.e. land use and wastewater discharge); from rather pristine to highly impacted rivers, flowing into the Black Sea, Baltic Sea, North Sea, Atlantic and the Mediterranean Sea. The samples were collected during different sampling campaigns, such as the German Monitoring of Small Streams (Liess et al., 2021; UFZ, 2018), the Joint Danube Survey 4 (ICPDR, 2019), an international sampling campaign supported by 13 participating European countries and the Elbe survey (Kamjunke et al., 2022), among others, between 2016 and 2019. The sites are located in Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Moldova, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine. The samples collected during the different projects through the different countries, cover more than 22 different river basins, including Amstel (2), Basque Country internal basins (20), Danube (127), Daugava (1), Ebro (5), Elbe (153), Ems (2), Gauja (1), Göta (2), Lielupe (1), Meuse (1), Oder (1), Porvoonjoki (1), Rhine (63), Scheldt (3), Schlei/Trave (2), Seine (2), Tajo (27), Vantaanjoki (1), Vejle (3), Warnow/Peene (4), Weser (12), estuaries (7), undisclosed geographic location (4). Further geographic information are provided in the supporting information (SI Appendix B, Table B.1).

2.2. Chemical analysis by LC-HRMS

All samples were analysed for 610 chemicals (SI Appendix B, Table B.2) with a consistent target screening approach using liquid chromatography high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS). The list of target compounds was compiled based on different criteria, including known occurrence of adverse effects, behaviour and occurrence in the environment and measurability by LC-HRMS.

From water sample aliquots of 1 mL, a volume of 5 μ L each was injected into the HPLC system (Ultimate 3000, Thermo Scientific), coupled to an HRMS (QExactive Plus, Thermo Scientific). Chromatographic separation was achieved using a Kinetex C18 EVO column (50 \times 2.1 mm, 2.6 μ m particle size) and by gradient elution with water (eluent A) and methanol (eluent B), each containing 0.1 % of formic acid. The flow rate was set to 300 μ L/min. After maintaining a mobile phase of 5 % B for the first minute, B was increased linearly to 100 % within 12 min and maintained for 11 min. The mass spectrometer was operated both in positive and negative electrospray ionisation mode sequentially (ESI+ and ESI-, respectively). The electrospray source and the transfer capillary of the mass spectrometer were operated at a temperature of 300 $^{\circ}$ C, a sheath gas flow of 45 a.u. and an auxiliary gas flow of 1 a.u.. The MS1 scan was set to a range of mass-to-charge (m/z) 100–1500 (full MS). At the beginning of each measurement sequence, 15 calibration standards were injected, including 483 compounds at concentrations between 0.1 and 5000 ng/L (SI Appendix B, Table B.2). For quality assurance (QA), an internal standard mix containing 38 isotope-labelled compounds (1 μ g/L), distributed over a wide retention time range (0.6–24.4 min) was added to each sample and calibration standard (SI Appendix B, Table B.3). Two calibration standards were re-injected at the end of each sequence for quality control (QC). An example sequence of a standard measurement batch, comprising 20 samples, can be found in the supporting information (SI Appendix B, Table B.4).

Subsequently, 127 compounds were added via retrospective analysis

(SI Appendix B, Table B.2). Again, 15 calibration standards of the new target compounds were injected and merged with the previous measurement files. For QC, 50 compounds were analysed both regularly (i.e. “calibration 1” and samples measured together) and retrospectively (i.e. “calibration 2” and samples measured separately). Deviations of less than 10 % were considered acceptable for the screening analysis performed.

LC-HRMS chromatogram files were converted from .raw into .mzML format by using ProteoWizard (version 3.0.18265) (Chambers et al., 2012) and processed with the open-source software MZmine (version 2.38) (Schulze, 2022a) in order to identify the compounds (peak picking, deconvolution, alignment, gap filling and peak annotation) (Pluskal et al., 2010), followed by semi-automated processing with the R package MZquant (version 2.38), which was used for quantification (Schulze et al., 2021). This involved normalisation to isotopically labelled internal standards, blank correction, and quantification of the target compounds using a generalised additive model based on at least four calibration points (“calibration 1”). Compounds, which could not be quantified by this semi-automatic workflow, i.e. due to varying retention times, were processed manually using the vendor software TraceFinder (version 4.1, Thermo Scientific).

For the retrospective analysis, the sample chromatograms (.mzML files) were re-processed using the second calibration sequence of 127 additional compounds (“calibration 2”). Retention time shifts were corrected by a model (Wagner, 2020) with the R package MZquant (version 2.38) (Schulze, 2022a). Based on the m/z ratio and the corrected retention times, the number of analysed target compounds increased to 610.

2.3. Identifying site-specific contaminants

The presence of site-specific contaminants was assessed in an explorative manner based on the fraction of the measured environmental concentration of compound i (MEC_i) and the 75th percentile of the MEC_i across all locations ($MEC75_i$).

$$\frac{MEC_i}{MEC75_i(NA = MDL_i)} > 1000 \quad (1)$$

In the case of singular detections, the $MEC75_i$ corresponds to the measured value (MEC_i). To exclude the possibility of falsely classifying individual substances as site-unspecific due to singular detections (or very low detection rates), not available (NA) values were replaced by the method detection limit (MDL) of each compound.

Except for the previously presented approach for identifying site-specific contaminants, missing values ($MEC_i < MDL$) were handled as NA values in this work. MDL values were determined on the basis of US-EPA guidelines (U.S. EPA, 2011).

2.4. Chemical footprints based on toxic units (TU)

Chemical footprints per compound were expressed by Toxic Units (TU) for relevant organism groups, including the water framework directive biological quality elements (BQE) algae (TU_{algae}), crustacean ($TU_{\text{crustacean}}$) and fish (TU_{fish}). TU were determined by normalizing environmental concentrations (i.e. exposure) to effect concentrations (e.g. EC_{50} , LC_{50} or IC_{50}) (Equation (2)) (Sprague, 1970; von der Ohe et al., 2009). The different effect categories included mortality, growth inhibition, population and movement inhibition. If available, experimental effect concentrations from the US EPA ECOTOXicology Knowledgebase (Olker et al., 2022) were used to calculate a statistical EC_{50} value representing the 5th percentile of all effect concentrations available per BQE. If no experimental data was available, predicted values (ECOSAR 1.0) based on the Chemprop 6.7.1 baseline toxicity model (UFZ, 2021) were used. Further details on the applied effect data are published in Schulze et al. (2021) and Finckh et al. (2022a). A summary of the applied effect concentration values is available in the supporting

information (SI Appendix B, Table B.2) and on Zenodo (Schulze, 2022b).

$$TU_{\text{BQE},i} = \frac{MEC_i}{EC_{50,\text{BQE},i}} \quad (2)$$

Footprints for the detected mixtures were estimated from summing up individual compound TU (Equation (3)) according to the mixture toxicity model of concentration addition and suggested as “screening level” risk assessment of chemical mixtures by Backhaus and Faust (2012).

$$\sum TU_{\text{BQE}} = \sum_{i=1}^n TU_{\text{BQE},i} \quad (3)$$

Mixture chemical footprints ($\sum TU_{\text{algae}}$, $\sum TU_{\text{crustacean}}$ and $\sum TU_{\text{fish}}$) can be compared to established thresholds for acute and chronic toxicity. Based on field observations (Beketov et al., 2013; Schäfer et al., 2012) and accepted acute-to-chronic ratios (Ahlers et al., 2006), Malaj et al. (2014) defined an acute threshold of 0.1 for all BQEs and BQE-specific chronic thresholds of 0.02 for algae, 0.001 for crustacean and 0.01 for fish. $\sum TU$ values exceeding the thresholds indicate the likelihood of acute and chronic ecological effects from exposure to the related chemical mixtures, respectively.

2.5. Urban discharge fraction (UDF)

A graph theory network (GTN) was established for each of the catchments based on the information given in the HydroShed database. Wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) with population equivalents (PE) of more than 2000 (EEA, 2020) were added as nodes to the GTN and all sampling sites of this campaign; undisclosed sampling sites were excluded. The accumulated urban discharge fraction (UDF) of the nearest upstream WWTP was used to characterise the influence of all upstream WWTPs on the measured compounds of a sampling site.

The accumulated urban discharge fraction was defined as a proxy for point source impacts as the percentage of water in the river that originates from WWTPs:

$$UDF = \frac{Q_U}{Q_U + Q_R} \quad (4)$$

where Q_U is the accumulated WWTP outflow in the river network, and Q_R is the discharge of the river at the location of the specific WWTP effluent. Q_U was calculated as sum of wastewater from households and small industries (Q_H), storm water (Q_{SW}), and sewer infiltration water (Q_{SIW}):

$$Q_U = Q_H + Q_{SW} + Q_{SIW} \quad (5)$$

where Q_H was estimated as population equivalents (PE) multiplied by the mean water usage per capita in the respective European countries (EurEau, 2021). Q_{SW} and Q_{SIW} were estimated as half of the amount of Q_H based on German data (Destatis, 2019):

$$Q_{SW} = 0.5 \cdot Q_H \quad (6)$$

$$Q_{SIW} = 0.5 \cdot Q_H \quad (7)$$

The river discharge (Q_R) was modelled by a mesoscale hydrological model (mHM) and provided on European scale in a 5 km grid (Kumar et al., 2013; Samaniego et al., 2010; Samaniego et al., 2019). Further information about the UDF and its calculation can be found in Büttner et al. (2022) and Yang et al. (2022).

2.6. Stream orders

The stream order is a widely used concept in hydrology describing the hierarchical structure of river networks (Horton, 1945; Strahler, 1957). The smallest streams have the order one. Downstream of the confluence of two streams of order one, there is a stream of order two.

Fig. 1. Chemical loads of target compounds in European streams. The size of the circles corresponds to the number of target compounds detected per sampling site. The bar plot displays the overall fraction of samples (in %) per number range of detected chemicals across all sites.

Two streams of order two build a stream of order three and so forth. The mean discharge and the dilution capacity is increasing with increasing stream order. Higher-order streams have larger catchment areas and receive more inputs from upstream sources, which can affect the ecological status of downstream reaches. Technically, the stream order depends on the resolution of the used river network. HydroShed data based on the 15 arc second resolution was used to obtain the stream order (Lehner and Grill, 2013; Linke et al., 2019).

2.7. Data evaluation and visualization

Basic data evaluation and visualization was performed with Microsoft Excel 2013 and with R (version 4.0.4) using R-studio (version 1.2.1335) including the libraries 'tidyverse' and the packages 'dplyr', 'ggplot2', and 'tidyr' for data wrangling and visualisation, 'data.table', 'ggfortify' and 'ggrepel'. The data was geo-referenced and visualised on maps with ArcGIS Pro (version 2.9) from Esri and edited in Microsoft PowerPoint 2013. GTNs were derived using ArcGIS (version 10.8.2) (arcpy) and Matlab (version R2023a).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Occurrence and concentration of chemicals in European streams

To date, this study constitutes the largest dataset of European sampling locations that have been analysed using a consistent and homogeneous approach with the objective to analyse mixture chemical footprints. Out of 610 compounds analysed, 504 were detected (MEC > MDL) in at least one out of 445 samples (SI Appendix B, Table B.5) (Finckh and Carmona et al., 2023). In 17 % of the samples only 1–25 compounds were detected, while 26–50, 51–100 and 101–200 compounds were found in 23 %, 41 % and 18 % of the samples, respectively (Fig. 1). In 1 % of the samples, more than 200 compounds were detected. The highest number of detected compounds was 241 belonging to a sample from the Danube River. Most of the compounds detected were pesticides and biocides (229), followed by different pharmaceuticals (175) and other chemicals (100), including surfactants, food, plastic and rubber additives, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), UV filters

and corrosion inhibitors.

The measured environmental concentrations (MEC) of the detected compounds ranged from 1 ng/L to 74 µg/L (3-cyclohexyl-1,1-dimethylurea). Detection frequencies per compound ranged from one site (0.2 %) to 339 sites (76 %) (Fig. 2A), with 96 compounds occurring in at least 25 % of the samples (Fig. 2C–D). The most frequently detected compound was the pharmaceutical metabolite N-acetyl-4-aminoantipyrine. Further frequently detected compounds, which occurred in at least 60 % of the samples were metolachlor–ethane sulfonic acid, a transformation product (TP) of the legacy herbicide metolachlor, the industrial compound m-xylene-4-sulfonic acid, the antiepileptic drug carbamazepine, as well as other pharmaceuticals including metformin, N-formyl-4-aminoantipyrine, tramadol; the sweeteners acesulfame, cyclamate and sucralose; the vulcanization accelerator/rubber component 1,3-diphenylguanidine, the corrosion inhibitor 5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole, the nicotine TP cotinine; the UV filters phenylbenzimidazole sulfonic acid and benzophenone-4, the herbicide bentazone and herbicide TP metazachlor ESA; and the industrial compound 4'-aminoacetanilide used to produce azo dyes and pharmaceuticals (Fig. 2C–D).

Comparing the list of target compounds with previous studies, many known and problematic organic micropollutants were considered. Of 182 micropollutants identified by Yang et al. (2022) posing toxic risks in the water environment according to the review of 83 prioritisation studies (i.e. Risk Quotients above one, RQ > 1), 63 compounds were analysed in the present study (SI Appendix B, Table B.2). All except one compound were detected in one or more samples. Among this list, there were only eleven compounds, which didn't belong to the chemical classes of pesticides and biocides or pharmaceuticals, such as the plastic additive triphenylphosphate, the corrosion inhibitor 1H-benzotriazole and the industrial chemicals perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOSA), 2,4-dinitrophenol, benzenesulfonic acid and 2,4-dichlorophenol.

In total, 216 compounds were found with maximum concentrations (c_{max}) of more than 1 µg/L, while 77 compounds comprised a c_{max} of more than 10 µg/L (SI Appendix A, Fig. A.1). Some of these occurred rather frequently (> 25 % of sites) (Fig. 2D) including 1,3-diphenylguanidine, sucralose, gabapentin-lactam, 1H-benzotriazole, candesartan, DEET, lamotrigine, oxypurinol, melamine, caffeine, hexa(methoxymethyl)melamine and guanylurea, to name only the top ten according

Fig. 2. Chemical compounds detected in European streams. (A) Detection frequencies of 504 organic micropollutants. The red line denotes a detection frequency of 25 %. (B) Maximum concentrations (c_{max}) of all compounds with $c_{max} > 1 \mu\text{g/L}$. (C) Detection frequencies of 96 compounds detected in more than 25 % of the samples. The number next to each bar represents the median concentration (c_{med}) in $\mu\text{g/L}$. (D) Maximum concentrations ($c_{max} > 1 \mu\text{g/L}$) of compounds detected in more than 25 % of the samples. The number next to each bar represents the maximum concentration (c_{max}) in $\mu\text{g/L}$. Pesticides and biocides are coloured in green, pharmaceuticals are coloured in blue, other chemicals are coloured in purple. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Concentrations of chemical compounds in surface water versus treated wastewater. Spearman correlation of the median of the chemical concentrations (c_{med}) for (A) pharmaceuticals, (B) pesticides and biocides and (C) other chemicals, and (D) all 332 compounds measured in both surface water and treated wastewater (according to the present study and Finckh et al. (2022a), respectively).

to c_{max} . However, also rarely detected chemicals (< 25 % of sites) (Fig. 2B) such as bisphenol S, p-toluenesulfonamide, cholic acid, 3-cyclohexyl-1,1-dimethylurea, chenodeoxycholic acid, azelaic acid, hexamethylenediamine, vancomycin, perfluorooctanesulfonamide (PFOSA) and 1-decanesulfonic acid were among these high-concentration chemicals, naming again the first ten compounds according to c_{max} .

In order to understand the relevance of site-specific contamination and sources vs. ubiquitous pollution, ratios of MEC and MEC75 larger than 1000 for at least one compound as shown in equation (1) were used as an indicator for sites with specific pollution. This phenomenon was found for 10 % of the sites (SI Appendix B, Table B.1), while site-specific

contaminants according to this approach comprised 10 pesticides and biocides and 25 other chemicals, such as plastic additives and different industrial chemicals, but no pharmaceuticals (SI Appendix B, Table B.6). The occurrence of so many point sources related compounds highlights the need for site-specific targeted monitoring based on known site-specific pollutants, in combination with suspect- and non-targeted screening methods.

Median concentrations of chemicals that have been reported by Wilkinson et al. (2022) in European rivers are well in agreement with those that have been found in the present study (> 25 %) with deviations by maximum a factor of ten suggesting comparable levels of contamination (SI Appendix A, Fig. A.2, SI Appendix B, Table B.2). The

Fig. 4. Risk driving chemical compounds in European streams. Toxic Unit ranges of the top 30 compounds sorted by maximum values for (A) algae, (B) crustacean and (C) fish. Boxplot hinges represent the 25th and 75th percentile, and the upper/lower whiskers $\pm 1.5 * IQR$ (interquartile range). The centre line represents the median concentration. The dashed line represents the acute risk threshold of 0.1, the bold line represents the chronic risk threshold of 0.02, 0.001 and 0.01 for algae, crustacean and fish, respectively (Malaj et al., 2014). Pesticides and biocides are coloured in green, pharmaceuticals are coloured in blue, other chemicals are coloured in purple. The asterisk denote compounds without available measured EC_x values (i.e. prediction-based TU values). Long compound names are annotated using abbreviations: didecyltrimethylammonium (DDAm), benzyldimethyldodecylammonium (BDDAm), N,N-dimethyldodecylamine (NNDDA), hexadecyltrimethylammonium (HDTMAM), hexadecylpyridinium (HDP), triphenyl phosphate (TPhP), thiophanate-methyl (TPM), 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPy), 2,4-dichlorophenol (2,4-DCP), 1,2-benzisothiazolinone (1,2-BIT), N,N-dimethyldodecylamine N-oxide (DDAO), tris(2-ethylhexyl)phosphate (TEHP), perfluorooctanesulfonamide (PFOSA), 4-nitroquinoline-1-oxide (4NQO), 2,4-dinitrophenol (2,4-DNP), triphenylphosphine oxide (TPPO), 2-octyl-4-isothiazolin-3-one (OIT), 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,3-pentanediol diisobutyrate (TXIB), tri-isobutylphosphate (TiBP), tetrachlorosalicylanilide (TSCA), 4-hydroxytamoxifen (4HT). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Chemical footprints of target compounds in European streams. (A–C) Maps showing which sites exhibit no risk (green), chronic risk (yellow) or acute risk (purple) according to risk thresholds introduced by Malaj et al. (2014) for (A) algae, (B) crustacean and (C) fish. For acute risks the threshold is $\sum TU = 0.1$. For chronic risks, the thresholds are $\sum TU_{\text{algae}} = 0.02$, $\sum TU_{\text{crustacean}} = 0.001$ and $\sum TU_{\text{fish}} = 0.01$. (D–F) Stacked bar plots of the number of compounds contributing to the threshold exceedance when the TUs of all detected compounds per sample were added cumulatively with increasing value for (D) algae, (E) crustacean and (F) fish. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

widespread distribution of pharmaceuticals and other organic micro-pollutants across European river basins illustrates the pervasiveness of pollution and the presence of common sources, such as treated and untreated wastewater.

3.2. Chemical concentrations in surface water versus wastewater

Assuming that urban discharges are one of the major pollution sources of surface waters in Europe, median concentrations of 332 compounds detected both in the present surface water samples and wastewater treatment plant effluents ($c_{med,SW}$ and $c_{med,WW}$, respectively) were correlated (Fig. 3) (SI Appendix B, Table B.7). Here, $c_{med,SW}$ was calculated based on the results of the present study, while $c_{med,WW}$ was taken from a previous wide-scope chemical target screening study by Finckh et al. (2022a).

Significant correlations ($p < 0.01$) were found for the full set of chemicals (Spearman correlation coefficient $R = 0.64$) as well as the subsets of pharmaceuticals ($r = 0.66$), pesticides and biocides ($r = 0.5$) and other chemicals ($r = 0.59$). Considering river sizes and the distances from the WWTP emissions, the substantial variability in the correlated association was expected. However, the smaller variability in the case of pharmaceuticals (i.e. largest R value) supported the hypothesis that particularly pharmaceuticals exhibit a common source in treated wastewater, indicating a close link between wastewater effluent composition and surface water quality. For 25 % of the pesticides and biocides, 68 % of the pharmaceuticals and 51 % of other chemicals, the ratio of $c_{med,SW}$ to $c_{med,WW}$ was below one, supporting the concept of surface water as a dilution of wastewater effluents with possible further removal by transformation or adsorption to sediments. Among these compounds, some frequently detected wastewater markers were found, such as carbamazepine, cotinine, different sweeteners (i.a. acesulfame, cyclamate and sucralose), as well as corrosion inhibitors (i.a. 5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole and 1H-benzotriazole); but also well-known biocides of urban use, including the herbicides terbutryn and diuron, the fungicide carbendazim and the insecticide fipronil, which are applied as antifoulants and against ectoparasites on pets. Rarely detected compounds have a higher likelihood of deviation from expected $c_{med,SW}$ to $c_{med,WW}$ ratios such as in the case of vancomycin, which has been detected in only three samples, but all at high concentrations ($c_{med,SW} = 73 \mu\text{g/L}$). Also the four biocides benzethonium, benzyltrimethylammonium, didecyltrimethylammonium and 3,4-dichlorophenylurea have been detected in few samples (4, 4, 5 and 1, respectively) and at high concentrations ($c_{med,SW} = 0.9, 1.2, 1.4$ and $0.4 \mu\text{g/L}$). The large percentage of pesticides and biocides with greater $c_{med,SW}$ than $c_{med,WW}$ concentrations (75 %) indicates, in general, sources other than municipal wastewater, mainly agricultural run-off.

3.3. Risk-based compound prioritisation

Prioritisation of chemicals according to individual chemical footprints using Toxic Units (TU) was based on measured effect concentrations from the US EPA ECOTOXicology Knowledgebase (Olker et al., 2022) for the biological quality elements (BQE) algae, crustaceans and fish (TU_{algae} , $TU_{crustacean}$, and TU_{fish}) for 26 %, 24 % and 28 % of the compounds, respectively (SI Appendix B, Table B.2). TU of compounds without available measured effect concentrations were calculated based on predicted effect values (ECOSAR 1.0), using a baseline toxicity model for green algae, daphnia and fish. All TU were compared to previously suggested thresholds for acute risks (0.1 TU for all BQEs) and chronic risks ($0.02 TU_{algae}$, $0.001 TU_{crustacean}$, and $0.01 TU_{fish}$) (Malaj et al., 2014).

For algae, the greatest individual chemical footprints were exhibited mainly by herbicides and some fungicides, as well as several quaternary ammonium compounds (QACs) often used as biocides (Fig. 4A). For 25 compounds TU_{algae} of more than 0.02 (chronic risk threshold) were found at one or more sites, while 14 of these compounds exhibited more

than $0.1 TU_{algae}$ (acute risk threshold), including ametryn (5.1), didecyltrimethylammonium (1.0), diuron (0.51), flumioxazin (0.42), spiroxamine (0.37), triclosan (0.28), flufenacet (0.21), benzyltrimethylammonium (0.19), terbutylazine (0.17), flufenoxuron (0.16), clarithromycin (0.14), orlistat (0.14), isoproteruron (0.14) and terbutryn (0.13).

For crustaceans, the greatest individual chemical footprints were found for pesticides and biocides, complemented by the pharmaceuticals orlistat and diclofenac and two industrial compounds (Fig. 4B). For 72 compounds, more than $0.001 TU_{crustacean}$ indicate exceedance of chronic risk thresholds at one or more sites, with 12 of these compounds exceeding even the acute risk threshold of $0.1 TU_{crustacean}$, including diazinon (486), imidacloprid (1.4), didecyltrimethylammonium (1.0), fipronil (0.29), 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (0.24), 2,4-dichlorophenol (0.21), fenthion (0.21), benzyltrimethylammonium (0.19), flufenoxuron (0.16), orlistat (0.14), diclofenac (0.11), carbendazim (0.11).

Only 13 compounds exhibited individually a significant footprint on fish exceeding chronic toxic risk thresholds, 6 of them exceeding also acute toxic risk thresholds, again, most of them pesticides and biocides. Among them were the QACs didecyltrimethylammonium (1.0) and benzyltrimethylammonium (0.19) together with dinoseb (0.31), carbendazim (0.25), flufenoxuron (0.16). Similar to the other BQEs, also the obesity drug orlistat (0.14) exceeded chronic and even the acute toxicity threshold for fish (Fig. 4C). However, it should be mentioned here that these are mostly prediction-based TU values (highlighted with an asterisk in Fig. 4), which require further experimental confirmation, as already discussed by Maurer et al. (2023) in the case of orlistat.

Besides the evident advantage of calculating TU values for risk-based compound prioritisation, there are four main limitations about this approach. (i) The use of baseline toxicity as a best-case assumption for compounds without measured effect data, even if they exert a specific mode of action. These predictions provide rather similar toxicity predictions across all three trophic levels, rather than discriminating particular sensitive ones. (ii) The use of non-standardised chronic and acute risk thresholds according to Malaj et al. (2014), which are based on field data for crustacean (i.e. studies reported shifts in invertebrate communities towards more tolerant species when exposed to pesticides at $1/1,000$ of the *Daphnia magna* LC_{50} values) and laboratory data for algae and fish (i.e. based on the empirical calculation of the ratio between acute LC_{50} and EC_{50} values and chronic NOEC and LOEC values for the same species and the same compound). (iii) Relevant natural and synthetic steroidal hormones were not acquired by the LC-HRMS screening due to insufficient detection limits to cover low but biologically active environmental concentrations, which, in particular, might contribute to chemical footprints on fish. (iv) Very hydrophobic compounds such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, pyrethroids or some halogenated pesticides cannot be analysed with the approach used in this study, but may contribute to the overall toxic risk.

3.4. Mapping of chemical footprints

Chemical footprints of the detected chemical mixtures exceeded the chronic toxicity thresholds for algae, crustacean and fish for 27 %, 74 % and 7 % of the samples, respectively, while 9 %, 15 % and 3 % of the samples exceeded even acute toxicity thresholds, respectively (Fig. 5A–C) (SI Appendix B, Tables B1 and B8–B10). For algae, chemical footprints exceeding chronic or acute thresholds were caused by one individual compound each at 17 % of the sites (75), by few compounds (2–5) at 9 % of the sites (41) and more than 5 compounds at 1 % of the sites (5) (Fig. 5D). For crustaceans, acute or chronic threshold exceedances were driven by only one compound at 25 % of the sites (111), by few compounds (2–5) at 35 % of the sites (157) and more than 5 compounds at 14 % of the sites (61) (Fig. 5E). Chemical footprints on fish (acute or chronic) were based on one compound only at 4 % of the sites (19), few compounds (2–5) at 2 % of the sites (11) while no sites were identified where more than 5 compounds contributed to footprints

Fig. 6. Distributions of chemical footprints according to stream orders. Chemical footprints (Σ TU) grouped by different stream orders for (A) algae, (B) crustacean and (C) fish. The data covers 328 out of 445 sampling sites. The bars are coloured according to risk threshold exceedance: no risk (green), chronic risk (yellow) and acute risk (purple). Some bars contain samples of two risk categories: no/chronic risk (light green) and chronic/acute risk (red). The mean value (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of each distribution are based on \log_2 -transformed data. Corresponding QQ-plots are shown in the supporting information (SI Appendix A, Fig. A.6). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

beyond threshold levels (Fig. 5F).

The maximum numbers of compounds contributing to Σ TUs beyond the chronic thresholds for algae, crustacean and fish were 14, 32 and 5, respectively. This indicates that particularly for crustaceans, chemical footprints are a result of exposure to mixtures of multiple contaminants, while for fish and algae, footprints are often driven by individual compounds or mixtures of 2–5 compounds, only. Beyond that, for 171 compounds, the measured environmental concentrations exceeded the respective environmental quality standard concentration (EQS) or predicted no-effect concentration (PNEC), indicating a non-acceptable risk from the regulatory perspective (SI Appendix B, Table B.11).

Mapping chemical footprints in European river basins indicates a distribution of contamination exceeding acute and chronic risk thresholds over all basins investigated, without a clear dependency on the geographical region under investigation, highlighting the need for improvement at European scale, although several European regions were not covered in this study. To summarise, based on typical water contaminants accessible with LC-HRMS screening and mainly driven by toxicity to crustaceans, 74 % of the investigated European stream sites exhibit risks of chronic adverse effects, while 18 % of the sites face footprints even beyond acute toxicity thresholds for one or more BQE (SI Appendix A, Fig. A.3). This situation might be further aggravated by metals (Couture and Pyle, 2011), very hydrophobic chemicals, endocrine disrupting steroids (Finckh et al., 2022b) and others, that were beyond the scope of this study (Santos et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2022). Thus, our results clearly indicate the widespread likelihood for adverse effects on different trophic levels of the aquatic ecosystem, which is well in agreement with previous investigations that identified chemical pollution as one of the major causes for reduced biodiversity (Beketov

et al., 2013; Liess et al., 2021) and an impaired ecological status (Lemm et al., 2021).

3.5. Relation of chemical footprints and the stream order

For the assessment of the dependency of chemical footprints on the stream order, the samples and their corresponding chemical footprints were grouped according to the Strahler stream order (Fig. 6). The mean (μ) of the distributions was found to be rather independent of the stream order, exceeding chronic thresholds, particularly for invertebrates. The fractions of samples exhibiting acute risks for one or more BQEs (i.e. algae, crustacean and fish) were 10 %, 29 %, 21 % and 15 % for increasing stream orders (i.e. 1–2, 3–4, 5–6 and 7–8, respectively). The width of the distribution, represented by the standard deviation (σ) or variance (σ^2), decreased for all BQE with increasing stream order. This observation was confirmed by the results of the Levene's test, which showed a significant difference in the variance of $\log_2(\Sigma$ TU) and the stream order for all three BQE ($p < 0.05$) (SI Appendix A, Table A.1). Further analysis using the Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test with Dunn's post-hoc test confirmed a significant difference between stream orders 1–2 (196 samples) and stream orders 3–8 (223 samples) (SI Appendix A, Tables A.2–A.5). Higher diversity of chemical footprints in headwater streams agrees with the assumptions, since these streams include pristine water bodies as well as creeks dominated by wastewater and agricultural run-off. Large rivers face more consistent chemical footprints due to large numbers of upstream contamination sources and higher dilution effects. The seven samples which exhibited an acute risk in the larger rivers (stream order 7–8) were located in the Danube river basin, mostly downstream of bigger sources such the general wastewater

Fig. 7. Chemical footprints (by percentage range) beyond the safe operating space. The map displays the fraction of sites where the measured chemical concentration exceeds the acute risk threshold (A) and the chronic risk threshold (B) for one BQE or more. Percentage ranges were adopted by Malaj et al. (2014). River basins are annotated by abbreviations: Danube (DN), Elbe (EL) and Rhine (RH). The exact percentages are listed in the supporting information (SI Appendix A, Table A.6).

collector of Novi Sad (Danube, Serbia) and Sabac (Tisza, Serbia) or at the mouth of the Tisza and Sava rivers to the Danube.

The findings demand for a general reduction of chemical emissions to the water cycle preventing impacts on water quality and ecosystems in European water bodies together with specific measures for the substantial percentage of small and medium size streams facing chemical footprints beyond acute toxicity levels by receiving hazardous discharges from domestic, industrial and agricultural pollution sources with insufficient dilution by uncontaminated water.

3.6. Chemical impact of urban discharges

The correlation between median wastewater effluent and surface water concentrations (Fig. 3) might suggest a close relationship between the urban discharge fraction (UDF), as the fraction of treated wastewater in the river at a specific sampling site, and the chemical footprint in the receiving water body. However, no significant correlations were found between \sum TU and UDF. The Spearman coefficients were $r = 0.23, 0.22$ and 0.20 for algae, crustacean and fish, respectively. (SI Appendix A, Fig. A.4). This is probably due to the enormous variability of wastewater effluent quality with several orders of magnitude based on \sum TU (Finckh et al., 2022a; Finckh et al., 2022b) and the fact that pesticides and biocides are the main drivers of chemical footprints, but only partly related to urban discharge from treated wastewater.

3.7. Chemical footprints in different river basins

In alignment with the original planetary boundary concept, the safe operating space is defined as the mixture exposure level leading to irreversible damage to earth's system processes (i.e. a point of no return). However, for the context of this study, it is described as the mixture exposure level that results in little to no harm (i.e. where impact thresholds are not exceeded). For the Elbe, the Danube and the Rhine river basin, the number of samples (153, 127 and 66, respectively) were considered sufficient for tentative conclusions on the percentage of sites outside the safe operating space in the basins. This holds for 80 %, 77 % and 63 % of the sites in the Danube, Elbe and Rhine basins exceeding chronic impact thresholds, respectively, with 24 %, 14 % and 10 % of the sites being exposed to acute toxic contamination (Fig. 7) (SI Appendix A, Table A.6). It should be mentioned, that the integration of samples from different campaigns with different objectives did not allow for a fully consistent representation of stream order distributions or sub-catchments, which might impact on the classification of the basins (SI

Appendix A, Fig. A.5). However, considering that there is no significant dependence of mean chemical footprint (μ) on stream orders (Fig. 6), the bias due to inconsistencies is considered negligible.

A comparison of the findings with the results by Malaj et al. (2014) (SI Appendix A, Table A.6), does not indicate any substantial reduction of chemical footprints on the level of the three river basins. The Elbe catchment even increased in both chronic and acute risk sites, while the fraction of sites in the Rhine basin with chemical footprints exceeding acute impact thresholds decreased. Although there is no direct comparability of both studies due to different compound sets, analytical methods and site selection, unacceptably high footprints at 74 % of 445 sites sampled all over Europe based on a consistent set of water contaminants give a strong indication for persisting pollution in European water bodies outside the safe operating space and confirm the need for action to reduce chemical footprints on the water cycle.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Saskia Finckh: Conceptualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Project administration. **Eric Carmona:** Conceptualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Project administration. **Dietrich Borchardt:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Olaf Büttner:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Martin Krauss:** Validation, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Tobias Schulze:** Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Soohyun Yang:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Werner Brack:** Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used DeepL and ChatGPT in order to improve language and readability. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Supplementary material

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